

TO STUDY THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TRAINING & DEVELOPMENT IN BANK EMPLOYEES OF JABALPUR CITY

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Abstract:

Training & Development is the major function of the Human Resource Management. The main objective of the training and development is to improve the performance and productivity of the employees. Training & Development means increasing an employee's ability to perform through learning through improving the employee's attitude or increasing his or her skills and knowledge." I have collected the data from 60 employees (Assistant Manager and clerical staff) working in public sector and private sector Bank in Jabalpur. From the research it is found that training and development exist in the banks and it helps to improve the efficiency of the employee. There is also the need of updating the employee training program in respect to make it more result oriented and cost efficient.

Key Words: Training, Human Resource Management, Skill & Programs

1. Introduction:

Training is a learning process in which employees get an opportunity to develop skill, competency and knowledge as per the job requirement. The main objective of the training program is to improve the work performances of the employees. Training will help develop to improve their performance in their job and also help to learn new technologies.

Development means learning opportunities which is designed to help employees to grow. It provides the general knowledge and attitudes, which will be helpful to employers in higher positions. Development is not skill oriented. These programs also help to prepare employees to handle higher responsibilities in the future.

2. Need of Training:

Individual Level:

- ✓ Diagnosis of present problems and future challenges
- ✓ Improve individual performance or fix up performance deficiency
- ✓ Improve skills or knowledge or any other problem
- ✓ To anticipate future skill-needs and prepare employee to handle more challenging tasks
- ✓ To prepare for possible job transfers

Group Level:

- ✓ To face any change in organization strategy at group levels
- ✓ When new products and services are launched
- ✓ To avoid scraps and accident rates

3. Identification of Training Needs (Methods):

Individual Training Needs Identification:

- ✓ Performance Appraisals
- ✓ Interviews
- ✓ Questionnaires
- ✓ Attitude Surveys
- ✓ Training Progress Feedback
- ✓ Work Sampling
- ✓ Rating Scales

Group Level Training Needs Identification:

- ✓ Organizational Goals and Objectives
- ✓ Personnel / Skills Inventories
- ✓ Organizational Climate Indices
- ✓ Efficiency Indices
- ✓ Exit Interviews
- ✓ MBO / Work Planning Systems
- ✓ Quality Circles
- ✓ Customer Satisfaction Survey
- ✓ Analysis of Current and Anticipated Changes

4. Review of Literature:

P. Akilandeswari, (2014) “A Study on Effectiveness of Training in Indian Banks” International Journal of Recent Advances in Organizational Behavior and Decision Sciences p.p-(85-99) in his study found that training and development are continuous process in improving the caliber of employees. It is an attempt to improve their current and future performance but the organization should keep a track on their performance after imparting them training .Therefore most of the commercial banks either private or public adopt training and development programmers at the time of induction, promotion and other situation. In this research paper an attempt is made to learn that training and development exist in banks and their impact to generate efficiency of employees to cater to the need of their customers.

Kavita Rani and Kurukshetra Diksha Garg In their study they process of financial development in India has hinged effectively on the development of banking system. Present research paper is of descriptive type and based on primary data collected through questionnaire filled by the bank employees. The present paper explained some suggestions to enhance training and development strategies, and to cope up with the existing challenges in the wake of severe competition in the training and development. The findings of the study suggest that training and development is inevitable and unavoidable in any sector

Raja Abdul Ghafoor Khan, Furqan Ahmed Khan and Dr. Muhammad Aslam Khan, “Impact of Training and Development on Organizational Performance” Global Journal of Management and Business Research p.p.-(62-68) in his study found that Training and Development, On the Job Training, Training Design and Delivery style are four of the most important aspects in organizational studies. we have proved them with the help of Results show that Training and Development, On the Job Training, Training Design and Delivery style have significant affect on Organizational Performance and all these have positively affect the Organizational Performance. It means it increases the overall organizational performance. We also prove our Hypothesis through empirical data. However, results are strongly based on the literature review.

5. Objective of the Study:

- ✓ To study training and development process in the banks for their employees
- ✓ To study the training and development programmers helps to the employees to perform their job
- ✓ To analyze the effect of training programs on the performance of employees.

6. Research Methodology:

The data collected for the study includes both primary data and secondary data. In primary data the authors had used structured questionnaire and intervned 60 employees (Assistant Manager and clerical staff) working in public sector and private sector Bank in Jabalpur. Sources like journals, newspaper, company reports and internet etc are used for secondary data.

7. Limitation of the Study:

- ✓ Research Report is limited to the employees who are working Banking Sector.
- ✓ It is difficult to understand the psychology of the employees.
- ✓ Training and Development program is costly Affair.

8. Data Analysis and Result:

Q1 Training program effectively contributed to improve ability in performing the job?

Alternatives	Response	Percentage
Yes	57	95 %
No	3	5%
Total	60	100%

From the above data it can be analyze from the data that 95% of employees agree that Training & Development Program improve the ability in performing the job whereas only 5% are disagree from the statement. It shows the awareness level of the employees regarding the training program conducted by the bank for improving their efficiency and updating their knowledge for bank policies and current market situations.

Q2 What is the Nature of the Training & Development Program?

Alternatives	Response	Percentage
Job oriented	42	70%
Promotion oriented	16	27%
Not Related to job	2	3%
Total	60	100%

Authors have analyzed from the data that 70% of employees told the Training & Development Program is related to the job. Which means effective training programs leads to effective development in employees which make their more specialized in their job. This help in easily achieving the company goals & objectives. Whereas 27% employees believe that it will help in them in getting promotion and 3% find it not related to their job.

Q3 Training programmes was relevant and useful?

Alternatives	Response	Percentage
Yes	40	67 %
Somehow	16	27%

No	4	6%
Total	60	100%

It can be concluded from the data that 67% of employees accepted that working become easier after the program as it was totally job oriented training, 27% said that their work is somehow related to training program as they need some more updated programs and only 6% did not find the program relevant and useful . This data shows the usefulness and need of training programme felt by the employee to get better understanding toward their work.

Q4 Do you think Training & Development Program helps to improve the performance of the employees?

Alternatives	Response	Percentage
Yes	38	63%
Somehow	15	25%
No	7	12%
Total	60	100%

Job oriented training and development program act as the backbone of any successful organization. The direct effect of training program on the employee's performance can see through this data. In this 63% of employee agreed that they had realized improvement in performance and efficiency after attaining training programs, 25% did not find much improvement in performance and 12% clearly disagree with the statement.

Q5 Do you think Training & Development Program are well planned?

Alternatives	Response	Percentage
Agree	40	67%
Neutral	16	27%
Disagree	4	6%
Total	60	100%

A systematic planned training & development program is the key source to improve individual performance or fix up performance deficiency therefore well planned training program is necessary. As per the data collected 67% of employee feels that training and development program is systematically planned and organized, 27% find some problem in coordinating the program and only 6% are dissatisfied.

Q6 Training program improved trainee's commitment towards job

Alternatives	Response	Percentage
Yes	36	60%
No	24	40%
Total	60	100%

60% of employees can relate it to their job and get motivated which help in improving their commitment toward their jobs, 40% disagree and find no relation between improvements in performance due to training program.

Q7 Training program helped to acquire better job satisfaction

Alternatives	Response	Percentage
Yes	57	95%
No	3	5%
Total	60	100%

As it is well known fact that effective training program help in improving the job performance which lead to better job satisfaction in employees. As the responses also prove this statement a huge number of employees 95% agree with it where as 5% of employee disagree with the statement.

Q8 Do you think Training & Development program is fruitful for your promotion?

Alternatives	Response	Percentage
Yes	45	75%
No	15	25%
Total	60	100%

Development of self, specialization and efficiency in work are the key for career growth of any employee. Training & development is directly or indirectly help in getting promotion to the employees. As it can be seen in the above table 75% which is huge percentage of employee agree with this where are 25% find it irrelevant.

Q9 Do you think Training & Development program leads to develop new technical skill?

Alternatives	Response	Percentage
Yes	32	53%
No	18	30%
Somehow	10	17%
Total	60	100%

If training programs are systematically planned it will be very beneficial for updating of employee skills and creating effective resource for the organization. 53% of employees agree with the statement that training &

development program leads to development of new technical skills, 30% employee disagree with the fact and 17% find it little bit source of development.

Q10 Do you think T&D reduces the stress level of employees.

Alternatives	Response	Percentage
Yes	41	68 %
No	7	12 %
No Idea	12	20%
Total	60	100%

If employees are provided with structured training program, so they are likely to achieve good result in their work. This can be seen in the above data 68% of employees feel due to proper training & development program they face less difficulty in achieving their predetermined task which reduce the stress in employee, 12% employees disagree with it any 20% employee have no idea about it.

9. Suggestion:

Bank has seen stellar growth over the past decade and it is the largest private sector bank in India, it is not without its fair share of problems related to various things. The Bank has focused on customer satisfaction and productivity of employees, but it has also faced high rates of employee turnover due to lack of employee focus. We present some of our suggestion to improve T&D activities over the coming years:

- ✓ Leadership potential assessment
- ✓ Identify the fast-trackers
- ✓ Nurture the talent so that can take future leadership roles
- ✓ Provide them the necessary environment to grow
- ✓ Expand the job so that it increases their overall responsibility and accountability
- ✓ Cross functional training should be done so that they can be absorbed in other job as well when the need arises
- ✓ Reassign and redesign responsibilities that the employee does not like or that are routine
- ✓ Provide more authority for the employee to self-manage and make decisions
- ✓ Invite the employee to contribute on a department or company level decisions and planning and business level organization goals
- ✓ Allow employees to pursue training and development in directions they choose and in the way they want, not just in company-assigned directions
- ✓ On the Job Training and Mentoring by senior employees should be encouraged
- ✓ Take into account peculiar characteristics of the region

10. Conclusion:

The conclusion of this study shows that Training & Development Program which is organized by the banking organisation is basically related with their job and employees also found that working become easier after the training programs. This program helps employee to perform better and also help to develop new technical skill. Training & Development program also fruitful for their promotion and future growth.

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